

DETERMINANTS OF DIETARY HABITS AMONG JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OBIO/AKPOR LGA, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Key words: Dietary habits, adolescents, socioeconomic status, social media marketing, cultural norms, Obio/Akpor, Rivers State	Abstract: <i>The purpose of this study was to examine the correlates of dietary practices of junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State. Two objectives, two research questions, and two hypotheses were proposed. The literature was reviewed using three frameworks: conceptual, theoretical, and empirical. The study used a descriptive cross-sectional design. The study's target population was 30,756 junior secondary school students from Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. A sample of 400 was drawn through a multi-staged sampling. Data was collected using researcher-developed questionnaire. The data was analysed using percentage and Point Biserial Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result reveals over half of the respondents 213(53.5%) had good dietary habit. In particular, 311(78.3%) of the students include salad when it is served, 271(68.3%) eat vegetables with their meals, 330(83.1%) eat breakfast daily and 211(53.1%) eat white bread, rather than wholemeal or brown bread. Statistically significant relationship was found between dietary habit and socioeconomic status ($n = 397, r = 0.64, p = 0.00$), social media marketing ($n = 397, r = 0.26, p = 0.00$), and cultural norms ($n = 397, r = 0.40, p = 0.00$). It was found that, the dietary habit of Junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was good and the factors affecting it were: socio-economic status, social media marketing, family size and cultural practices It was recommended, among other things, that parents should try to ensure that they teach their children healthy eating habit by providing healthy foods to their children. In addition, the parents/guardians should monitor the dietary habit of their children/wards by making sure they eat healthy foods.</i>
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Introduction

Adolescent nutrition is a critical public health issue as the dietary habit formed this period exerts long term consequences that reach adulthood. In a country that's plagued with a dual burden of malnutrition-under nutrition and over nutrition, it is imperative to understand the

determinants of dietary habits among junior secondary school students. Barb and Carolyn (2016) opined that diet is the food and beverage eaten and drunk daily by a person. Smith (2014) also observed that different classes of foods make up a diet that is consumed in response to the body needs. A dietary habit is the regular eating

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of diet that ensures the nutritional health of body (Marija et al., 2014). The decision on food items to be consumed is a personal choice but it is mainly influenced by the consumer's knowledge of nutrition, food and the facilities to make good choices of healthy diet, it is therefore essential to establish guidelines to enable individuals to make nutritionally beneficial choices since there are six classes of essential nutrients for human survival: carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, vitamins, minerals and water (Prince et al., 2020). The balanced diet has the different classes of food in the correct proportion for the adolescent to grow healthily.

In this study, dietary habits are habitual diet pattern consumed by students in junior secondary schools to maintain nutritional status of their body. Adolescent healthy diet is essential for physical, psychological and cognitive development. A healthy diet should be varied. Adolescents have different dietary patterns. Eating a healthy diet with plenty of fruit and vegetables, grains and protein-rich foods but little processed food can help adolescents to consume a nutritious diet and prevent chronic diseases such as overweight and obesity, type 2 diabetes and heart disease (NHS, 2018).

An unhealthy diet is also linked to nutrition transition. Many adolescents have substituted their healthy diet with fast foods which are predominantly made with saturated and trans-fats that contain low fibre, the rate of diet-related non-communicable diseases has never been higher as a consequence of shifts from high-fibre diets to overseas fast food diets (Sun et al., 2024). The WHO (2013) reported that diet is a risk factor for major health problems. It also

indicated that consumption of foods high in fat, sugars and other unhealthy nutrients (energy dense foods) and low levels of physical activity are among the drivers of non-communicable diseases and of particular note are the growing unhealthy diets and low levels of physical activity among children and adolescents (WHO, 2013).

Poor dietary habit leads to health problems due to malnutrition. Adolescents who are malnourished have an increased risk of delivering low birth weight infants, intra-uterine growth restriction, preterm birth, high infant mortality and poor child outcomes, as well as obstructed labour and other complications of pregnancy (Yu et al., 2016).

The factors which may influence dietary habits of junior high school students include: Parental socioeconomic status, Marketing through advertisements and social media, Family size and family culture. Parental socioeconomic status includes a number of factors such as income level and educational attainment. Household income definitely influences the expenditure on food. And food expenditure would probably rise in households with higher income resulting in a rise in dietary intake of the teenagers in the family. Parents' education is also a predictor of dietary habits of their children, that is, the greater the education level of parents, the better is the child rearing and care.

Junk food advertising has played a major role in the dietary habits of teenagers. Products advertised are usually junk foods, containing saturated fats, sugars, salt and sodium. Adolescents are easily influenced by these ads and want to buy the products being advertised. Most adolescents' eating preferences are shaped

by food ads. This includes all types of food, such as pizza, chocolate, biscuits, fruit juice and even healthy drinks.

A high rate of transition towards unhealthy dietary pattern is growing among adolescents. The study showed that the quality of diet deteriorates in adolescence; consumption of fruit, vegetables, milk and fruit juice are reduced while the consumption of junk food such as soft drinks is increased. There is the inclination to choose and consume foods that they love a lot because of the taste, popularity, affordability or peer pressure without considering the nutritional quality of the foods. The researcher has observed some of the adolescents in schools in the study area to be eating more meat, animal fat, milk, sugar and drinks, including: ice-cream, soft drinks and to eat less fruit and vegetables, cereals and starch. This is a concern for health and well-being of adolescents in Obio/akpor, LGA. Therefore this study aimed to investigate the determinants of dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State. Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formed to guide the study:

1. What are the dietary habits of junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among

junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive cross sectional design with the study carried out in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State. The study population comprised 30,756 junior secondary school students across 27 schools in the 2019/2020 academic session. A target sample size of 400 students was derived from the Taro Yamane formula, and 397 questionnaires were eventually found suitable for analysis after data cleaning. A multistage sampling procedure was used. Students were first grouped into public and private school clusters. Ten schools were selected from each cluster through simple random sampling, after which systematic sampling was applied to select participants within the chosen schools. Data were collected with a structured questionnaire titled Determinants of Dietary Habits among Junior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor LG (DDHJSSOBLG). The dietary behaviour section was adapted from the Adolescent Food Habits

Checklist developed by Johnson, Wardle, and Griffith (2002), while the first section captured socio-demographic variables and the proposed determinants of dietary habits, including parental income level, exposure to food advertising on social media, household size and culture-related food influence. The instrument undergo a face and content validation by three experts drawn from health education, sociology and statistics. Reliability was established through a test-retest procedure among thirty students outside the study population, producing a reliability coefficient of 0.88, which indicates good consistency. Data collection was interviewer-administered, with support from

two trained research assistants and prior permission obtained from school authorities. Completed questionnaires were coded and analysed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise dietary habit indicators, while point-biserial correlation was applied to examine relationships between the binary dietary habit outcome and the selected determinants at a significance threshold of 0.05.

Results

Research question 1: What are the dietary habits of junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Dietary Habits of Junior Secondary School Students (n = 397)

SN	Items	Yes F(%)	No F(%)	Total F(%)
1	Usually ate a piece of fruit every day.	196(49.4)	201(50.6)	397(100)
2	Usually eat fresh fruit, rather than biscuit	142(35.8)	255(64.2)	397(100)
3	Usually eat salad when it is available.	311(78.3)	86(21.7)	397(100)
4	Usually eat vegetables with meals.	271(68.3)	126(31.7)	397(100)
5	Usually eat chips more than once a week.	162(40.8)	235(59.2)	397(100)
6	Eat sweets or chocolate every day.	146(36.8)	251(63.2)	397(100)
7	Eat cakes, biscuits, or pastries every day.	192(48.4)	205(51.6)	397(100)
8	Usually drink fizzy drinks or soft drinks every day.	184(46.3)	213(53.7)	397(100)
9	Usually eat fried foods more than once a week.	232(58.4)	165(41.6)	397(100)
10	Usually add butter, margarine, or oil to vegetables or potatoes.	174(43.8)	223(56.2)	397(100)
11	Usually eat crisps (potato chips) every day.	166(41.8)	231(58.2)	397(100)
12	Eat white bread rather than brown bread.	211(53.1)	186(46.9)	397(100)
13	Usually have breakfast every day.	330(83.1)	67(16.9)	397(100)
14	Eat more than one portion of fruit each day.	161(40.6)	236(59.4)	397(100)
15	Eat more than one portion of vegetables each day.	167(42.1)	230(57.9)	397(100)

16	Usually have chips, or crisps more than once a week.	148(37.3)	249(62.7)	397(100)
17	Usually drink fruit juice every day.	171(43.1)	226(56.9)	397(100)
18	Eat fast food (e.g., burgers, kebabs, fried chicken) more than once a week.	129(32.5)	268(67.5)	397(100)
19	Eat more than one sweet or chocolate bar each day.	123(31.0)	274(69.0)	397(100)
20	Eat more than one packet of crisps each day.	134(33.8)	263(66.2)	397(100)
21	Eat more than one cake, biscuit, or pastry each day.	174(43.8)	223(56.2)	397(100)
22	Eat more than one packet of sweets each day.	100(25.2)	297(74.8)	397(100)
23	Usually eat whole meal or brown bread	219(55.2)	178(44.8)	397(100)
	Overall	184(46.5)	213(53.5)	397(100)

Guide: $\geq 50\%$ = good dietary habit; $< 50\%$ = poor dietary habit

Table 1 displays the respondents' dietary habits. In all, 53.5 percent of the 213 participants followed a healthy eating plan. As an example, 311 people (or 78.3% of the total) often consume salad whenever it's available, 271 people (or 68.3% of the total) typically include vegetables in their meal, 330 people (or 83.1% of the total)

Table 2: Point Biserial Correlations analysis showing relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA

Variables		Dietary Habit	Socio-economic	Remark
Dietary habit	Correlation coefficient	1	0.64	High relationship
	n	397	397	
Socio-economic status	Correlation coefficient	0.64	1	
	n	397	397	

typically have breakfast every day, and 211 people (or 53.1% of the total) typically choose white bread over whole grain or brown bread.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

This study examined the correlation between students' socioeconomic position and their eating habits in Obio/Akpor LGA's junior secondary schools, and the results are shown in Table 2. The study showed a strong link, with a correlation value of 0.64. Thus, among junior

Table 3: Point Biserial Correlations analysis showing relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA

Variables		Dietary Habit	Social media marketing	Remark
Dietary habit	Correlation coefficient	1	0.26	Low relationship
	n	397	397	
Social media marketing	Correlation coefficient	0.26	1	
	n	397	397	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = extremely low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80+ = very high association.

Table 3 shows the Point Biserial Correlations study of the association between social media marketing and food habits among junior secondary school students in the Obio/Akpor LGA. The results showed a correlation value of $r = 0.26$, indicating a modest link. Thus, the link

secondary school pupils in the Obio/akpor local government region, there was a substantial correlation between socioeconomic level and food preferences.

Research Question Three: What is the relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

between social media marketing and eating habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA was weak.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Point Biserial Correlations analysis showing relationship between socioeconomic status and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA

Variables		Dietary Habit	Socio-economic	Decision
Dietary habit	Correlation coefficient	1	0.64	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	n	397	397	
Socio-economic status	Correlation coefficient	0.64	1	
	Sig	0.00*		
	n	397	397	

***Significant; p<0.05**

Table 4 displays the results of the Point Biserial Correlations study on the correlation between students' socioeconomic class and their eating habits in Obio/Akpor LGA's junior secondary schools. The results showed that food habits were significantly related to socioeconomic position (n = 397, r = 0.64, p = 0.00), with a p-value less than 0.05. Therefore, among junior secondary school

students in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State, the null hypothesis that there is no significant association between socioeconomic level and food habits was rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Point Biserial Correlations analysis showing relationship between social media marketing and dietary habits among junior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA

Variables		Dietary Habit	Social media marketing	Decision
Dietary habit	Correlation coefficient	1	0.26	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.00*	
	n	397	397	
Social media marketing	Correlation coefficient	0.26	1	
	Sig	0.00*		

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*Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 5 displays the results of the Point Biserial Correlations study on the correlation between Obio/Akpor LGA junior secondary school students' food habits and social media marketing. The findings showed that dietary habits were significantly related to social media marketing ($n = 397$, $r = 0.26$, $p = 0.00$), with a p-value less than 0.05. As a result, we can say that junior high school students in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State, are more likely to change their eating habits after seeing social media ads for such products.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are discussed below:

In all, 53.5 percent of the 213 participants followed a healthy eating plan. In particular, 311 people (or 78.3% of the total) often consume salad whenever it is served, 271 people (or 68.3% of the total) typically include vegetables in their meal, 330 people (or 83.1% of the total) typically consume breakfast on a daily basis, and 211 people (or 53.1% of the total) typically choose white bread over whole grain or brown bread. In a study conducted by Wang et al. (2021) on adults in Jiangsu Province, China, they found that certain dietary patterns were associated with overweight and obesity. These patterns included the traditional diet, which included poultry, light-colored vegetables, red meat and its products, cereals and tubers products, condiments, oils, and dark-colored vegetables.

Another pattern was the fruit-egg diet, which included fruit, whole grains, pickled vegetables, eggs, and egg products. Lastly, there was the nut-wine diet, which included nut, wine, and pastry snacks. This study's results are consistent with those of López-Contreras et al. (2020), who found a healthy eating habit among children who were overweight. Consistent with previous research showing healthy eating habits among Saudi university students, this study's results corroborate those of Syed et al. (2020). The uniformity of the research may explain why the two studies showed such striking similarities. Zhu et al. (2021) examined the eating habits and exercise routines of Shanghai, China's middle and high school kids and found that they had a bad dietary pattern; our study found the opposite to be true. In addition, the results of this study contradict the findings of Poličnik et al. (2024) about the nutritional habits of teenagers and how well they conform to the guidelines for healthy and sustainable eating, which revealed an unhealthy eating pattern. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is because the research area was different.

The results showed that food habits were significantly related to socioeconomic position ($n = 397$, $r = 0.64$, $p = 0.00$), with a p-value less than 0.05. This research's results are in line with those of an Israeli study on teenage eating habits conducted by Sinai et al. (2021) that also found a strong correlation between socioeconomic status

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and eating habits. This research's results corroborate those of Mumena (2024), who found a correlation between socioeconomic class and eating habits in her study on Saudi diet quality. Consistent with previous research, this data confirms a correlation between socioeconomic status and eating behaviors among young adults and adolescents (Desbouys et al., 2020). The results are consistent with those of Voráčová et al. (2016), who demonstrated that socioeconomic disparities in dietary habits significantly affect adolescent health.

The findings showed that dietary habits were significantly related to social media marketing ($n = 397$, $r = 0.26$, $p = 0.00$), with a p-value less than 0.05. Amson et al. (2024) found a correlation between social media marketing and dietary habits in their study titled "Beyond the Screen: Exploring the Dynamics of Social Media Influencers, Food Marketing, and Gendered Influences on Adolescent Diets." Our findings are consistent with theirs. Patil et al. (2024) found a substantial correlation between social media marketing and food habits among Nigerian adolescents, which is consistent with the current study's findings.

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Conclusion

Based on the study, it was found out that, the dietary practices of Junior secondary school students in Obio/akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was good and the factors were: socio-economic background, social media advertising, family size and cultural practices.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were put forward based on the findings of the study:

1. The parents should make effort to ensure they inculcate healthy eating habits into their children by making available healthy foods for the children.
2. Parents/guidance should watch closely the dietary habit of their children/wards by ensuring that they consume healthy foods.
3. The children should also cooperate with their parents in controlling their nutritional practices, especially those with large family size.
4. The school management should also make their contribution by ensuring that they keep reminding the students about the importance of healthy dietary habit.

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